

Impact of Advertisement on FMCG Products in Tiruvarur Town, Tamil Nadu

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Abstract

The present study was aimed at investigating the impact of advertisement on FMCG products. Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) are products that are required by almost all users in their day to day life. The advertisement for these products needs more attention in terms of creating awareness among the consumers for their purchase decision. Thus, the current effort intends to study whether the advertisements for FMCG products are effective in creating awareness. For this purpose, primary data were collected from sample respondents using a well – structured questionnaire. Appropriate statistical analysis tools such as Chi – square test and descriptive statistics were used and it is found that the taste, quality, convenient price, packing attraction, understandability of the FMCG advertisements have major influence in creating awareness amongst the consumers..

Keywords: FMCG, Advertisement, Consumer, Taste, Packing attraction, Quality, Convenient price, Effectiveness.

Introduction

In the competitive world, the FMCG product plays an important role in every country. Now-a-days, the participations of competitors are highly increased in the field of fast moving consumer goods industry. Advertisement is an important medium through every FMCG industries to survive in the long run. Every company should be well aware about the advertisement medium which will help to withstand and stay long period maturity in the high competitions market that leads to the every company achieve success. So, the impact of advertisement plays a crucial role in the field of FMCG world.

Fast-moving consumer good (FMCG) are products that are rapidly sold for lower cost. Examples, Non-durable products like soft drinks, over-the-counter drugs, processed foods, toiletries and many other consumable products. In contrast, durable products such as kitchen appliances are commonly replaced over a period of some years.

We are living in the world of information where advertising has a crucial effect on viewers mind. Information can be spread via newspaper, magazines, television and internet etc. The FMCG industry in India is growing meticulously in last few years. Although India's local products have less demand as compared to the international brands. There are currently 32 Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG) companies in India. The FMCG products are escalating due to the reason of bombarded advertisements among people which stimulate them to purchase it. Advertisers spend much amount of investment while advertising their product so they keep their focus on several factors such as taste, quality, convenient price, packing attraction, understandability so that they can influence consumer mind with advertisements. Researchers would like to ascertain the impact of advertising on FMCG products in Tiruvarur Town, Tamil Nadu. None of the researchers has been done in the same media so far.

Review of Literature

According to **Ankit Katiyar, and Nikha Katiyar, (2014)** The FMCG products of bathing soap have seen a rush forward in their sales. More peoples are experimenting through their idea and try out newer bath soap. This study covers various factors that persuade the buying behaviour of consumer to purchase or consume the bath soap. **Chakraborty, et al. (2013)** says that the product promotion is a effective tool which motivate and direct the consumers who are travelling by way of tangential path. This will help the consumers to switch over from one brand to another brand. **According to Chitra. R (2014)** in her study explains that the purchasing plan of the customers towards branded apparel always influenced by several factors like perceived quality and emotional value. **Nasrudeen .R and Mohamed, (2014)** says that in the seventies, the green revolution provide expected boost to the agricultural rural economy in the country. Consequently, many firms started screening interest in rural markets and broaden their access to attain smaller village and towns. Additionally, now-a-days, the customers staying in the rural areas are behaving like urban consumers towards the urban standards of living, fashion, preference, taste etc. **Rajasekaran, B and Saravanan, P. A. (2014)** explains in their study throws on the attitudes, values, beliefs and perception of the consumers with regards to the utilization of fast moving consumer goods. To study the brand preference of fast moving consumer goods, the preference and belief of consumer towards trendy brands have been taken into concern. **Awan and Arif (2015)**, says that the customers are very much attracted in the media of advertisement by the use of celebrity endorsement. Awan and Hassan (2015) says that the marketing via SMS is a trendy tool of introducing products and services that will attracting new customers. Awan & Shahid says that the green marketing strategies are successfully proved that it is highly attract the educated customers. **Oh & Xu (2003)** says that the mass media influence the people's lives and thinking style. Advertisement influences the buying behaviour of the peoples. . **Rasool, et al (2012)** reveals that the advertisement about brand plays a important role to induce the consumers to purchase the same brands. It enlarges the performance of any business and its image among the competitor market. **Chen et al. (2008)** emphasize that the informative advertisement gives awareness to the consumers, so that they will like to purchase preferred goods. **Bashir and Malik (2009)** explain that now-a-days the consumers are very conscious in price in our society. Peoples are almost behaving rationally due to the benefits of the cost.

Objectives

- To study the impact of advertisement on FMCG product.
- To analyze which factors most influencing by advertisement.

Research Methodology

Research methodology is a route to scientifically solve the research problem in which the researchers adopted various steps that are commonly in his study along with the reason at the back of them. It is obligatory for the researcher to identify not only the research methods but also the tactic of methodology. A research design is the map of conditions of gathering and examination of data in a mode that aims to mingle relevance to the research purpose with cost-cutting measure in course of action. In point of fact, the research design is the arrangement of theoretical framework in which the research is conducted. It constitutes the blueprint for the gathering measurement and examination of collected data. A questionnaire was structured to know the viewpoint of people in Tiruvarur regarding the impact of advertisement in the FMCG product. The data for the study is collected with the help of primary and secondary data. The period of the study covers the range of 6 months from March to August. Convenience sampling technique is adopted for this study. It means that sampling units are chosen primarily on the basis of convenience of the researcher and the respondents. The size of the sample is restricted to 120 respondents selected through questionnaire. The data gathered from the respondents were put in the percentage and chi – square analysis to know the various factors and dependability of the variables. Various kinds of tables and charts are used to represent the survey findings and results.

Hypothesis Formulation

H1: There is no association between gender and consumer behaviour

Result Analysis

This is an analytical study from May to July 2018. A questionnaire was designed to know the point of view of people in Tiruvaar regarding the impact of advertisement on FMCG products in Tiruvarur town, Tamilnadu.

Table No. 1
Socio-Economic Factors of the respondents

S.No	Factors		No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Gender	Male	51	43
		Female	69	57
	Total		120	100
2.	Educational qualification	Diploma holder	22	18
		Graduate	57	48
		Post graduate	19	16
		Others	22	18
	Total		120	100
3.	Age	Below 18 years	29	24
		19 to 28 years	49	41
		29 to 38 years	22	18
		39 & Above	20	17
	Total		120	100
4.	Marital Status	Married	48	40
		Unmarried	72	60
	Total		120	100

Source: Primary Data

The above table depicts that socio-economic factors of the respondents in which the samples recorded the highest response rate from female of 57 percent than male of 43 percent, Educational qualification reveals that the 48 percent of the majority respondents are graduates, Distribution of respondent by their age shows that 41 percent of the majority respondents are 19 to 28 years and their marital status reveals that 60 percent of the majority respondents are unmarried.

Chi - Square Analysis

H1: There is no association between Gender and brand preference of the consumer

Table No.2

Chi-Square Test

Observed Frequencies	Expected Frequencies	(O - E) ²	(O - E) ² / E
15	14	(15 - 14) ²	1 / 14 = 0.071
14	14	(14 - 14) ²	0 / 14 = 0
12	14	(12 - 14) ²	4 / 14 = 0.286
10	9	(10 - 9) ²	1 / 09 = 0.111
18	19	(18 - 19) ²	1 / 19 = 0.053
19	19	(19 - 19) ²	0 / 19 = 0
20	18	(20 - 18) ²	4 / 18 = 0.222
12	13	(12 - 13) ²	1 / 13 = 0.077
			0.82

$$X^2 = \sum (O - E)^2 / E = 0.82$$

$$V = (r - 1) (c - 1) = (4 - 1) (2 - 1) = 3 * 1 = 3$$

$$\text{For } v = 3 \quad X^2_{0.05} = 7.81$$

The calculated value is much less than the table value. The null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, there is no association between gender and brand preference of the consumers of FMCG products.

Limitations

1. The present research has several limitations. The first limitation was about the sample selection because the entire sample is taken just from the Tiruvarur town.
2. Second, Limited companies of FMCG products were used in this research for getting the consumer preference

Findings

After analysis of the findings, the study concludes that the FMCG products on reach and create consciousness by means of effective display place of advertising media. Advertisement was effective in providing superior reach and creates awareness about the FMCG brands among the peoples. The research established that the preference of the consumers are highly influenced by the taste, quality, convenient price and packing attraction.

There is no significant association between gender and brand preference of the consumer was found as the magnitude of 7.81. The study also concludes that advertising has significant relationship with buying decision of the consumers. In addition, there is a positive relationship between gender and brand preference. This implies that companies have to be very conscious in the quality, taste, price and package factors which increase their market share.

Suggestions

Marketers have to make creative advertisement to satisfy consumers. The advertisement messages have to be clear because the common consumers can also understand them easily. The advertisement of FMCG products have not to be false and misleading and the quality of these advertisements has to be improved. Surprising advertising like latest addition is coming soon is also very constructive to stimulate the consumers. Convenient price of FMCG products attracts the consumers to buy products. The marketers have to observe the consumer continuously while preparing the advertisement message. The advertisement has to be interested in nature and it has to be ethics in nature. The awareness of advertisement will very helpful to catch the attention of the consumers towards the desired FMCG.

Conclusion

The present study concluded that, success of many businesses depends on their ability to create and retaining the customers. The advertisements have great impact on FMCG products. Here, there is no any association between gender and brand preference of the consumers of FMCG products. The advertisement can change the mind of the all types of consumers. The various media of advertisement grab the more attention among the consumers. The advertisement should not be too expensive. Because, the advertisement leads to increase the price of the product. The quality, packing attraction, taste and price of the products are highly influencing the preference of the consumers day-to-day. The consumers while watching the advertisements at many times that automatically stimulate the consumers to visit and purchase the advertised products. Finally, the study proved the advertisement plays a vital role with reference to FMCG products of consumer in Tiruvarur town, Tamilnadu.

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